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Research Paper

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Towards Human Papillomavirus Infection and Vaccination Among Undergraduate Medical Students and Interns: An Institution-Based Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Human papillomavirus (HPV) infection is a major public health concern and a leading cause of cervical cancer and other anogenital malignancies. Despite the availability of effective vaccines, HPV vaccination coverage remains suboptimal in India. Medical students, as future healthcare providers, play a crucial role in disseminating correct information and promoting preventive practices. **Objectives:** To assess the knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding HPV infection and HPV vaccination among undergraduate medical students and interns. **Materials and Methods:** An institution-based cross-sectional study was conducted among undergraduate medical students (1st to 4th year) and interns at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital. All eligible students (n = 653) were invited to participate. Data were collected using a structured, pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire. A total of 272 participants completed the questionnaire and were included in the final analysis. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics. **Results:** Most respondents were aware of HPV infection and its association with cervical cancer. However, gaps were observed in detailed knowledge regarding modes of transmission, vaccine schedule, and eligibility criteria. Attitude towards HPV vaccination was generally positive. Despite this, actual vaccination uptake among participants was low. **Conclusion:** Although awareness and attitudes towards HPV vaccination were satisfactory, deficiencies in knowledge and poor vaccination practices persist. Targeted educational interventions and institutional vaccination programs are recommended to improve HPV-related preventive practices among medical students

INTRODUCTION

Human papillomavirus (HPV) is one of the most common sexually transmitted infections

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worldwide and is strongly associated with cervical cancer, which remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality among women, particularly in developing countries. Persistent infection with high-risk HPV genotypes is implicated in the pathogenesis of nearly all cases of cervical cancer, as well as other anogenital and oropharyngeal cancers.¹ Prophylactic HPV vaccines have demonstrated high efficacy in preventing HPV infection and associated precancerous lesions when administered before exposure to the virus.² Despite the proven effectiveness and safety of these vaccines, HPV vaccination coverage remains low in many regions, including India, due to lack of awareness, misconceptions, sociocultural barriers, and vaccine hesitancy.³ Medical students and interns represent future healthcare providers who will play a key role in counselling patients, recommending vaccination, and implementing preventive strategies. Their knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding HPV infection and vaccination can significantly influence public acceptance and uptake of the vaccine. Assessing these parameters is essential to identify gaps and guide educational interventions. The present study was undertaken to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practices towards HPV infection and vaccination among undergraduate medical students and interns at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An institution-based cross-sectional study was conducted at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital of Sonitpur district of Assam. The study population included undergraduate medical students from 1st year to 4th year MBBS and interns enrolled during the study period, from 1st November, 2025 to 30th November, 2025. Inclusion criteria included all undergraduate students and interns who gave consent. Exclusion criteria included: (1) undergraduate students who

were absent during the period of study and (2) those who were unwilling to participate. All eligible students and interns were invited to participate (n = 653). These included 125 first-year students, 128 second-year students, 123 third-year students, 133 fourth-year students, and 144 interns. Participation was voluntary. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire developed after reviewing relevant literature. The questionnaire consisted of four sections: sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge regarding HPV infection and vaccination, attitude towards HPV vaccination, and practices related to HPV vaccination. The tool was pre-tested and modified for clarity. The questionnaire was distributed electronically after obtaining informed consent. A total of 272 participants completed the questionnaire and were included in the final analysis, yielding a response rate of 41.6%. Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using descriptive statistics. Results were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Tezpur Medical College and Hospital. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were maintained.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Of the 653 undergraduate medical students and interns eligible to participate in the study, 272 completed the questionnaire, resulting in a response rate of 41.6%. The breakdown of participants by academic year is shown in Table 1. Most participants were in their third year MBBS (40.1%), followed by second year (18.8%), fourth year (15.4%), interns (14.7%), and first year (11.0%). The inclusion of students from all academic years enabled a holistic assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practices at various points of medical education.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS ACCORDING TO ACADEMIC YEAR (N = 272)

Academic Year	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
1st year MBBS	30	11.0
2nd year MBBS	51	18.8
3rd year MBBS	109	40.1
4th year MBBS	42	15.4
Interns	40	14.7
Total	272	100

Knowledge Regarding HPV Infection and Vaccination

The participants' knowledge of HPV infections was adequate. 93.0% of the participants, identified the link between chronic HPV infections and cervical cancer. This is consistent with the global research with the causal link between high-risk HPV types and cervical cancer, as observed in the Global Cancer Statistics 2018, GLOBACON, by Bray et al. (2018)¹. Healthcare students in India also reported similar awareness according to Pandey et al. (2012)⁴ and Mehta et al. (2013)⁵, implying that the awareness of cervical cancer and sexually transmitted infections is sufficiently covered in the undergraduate teaching curriculum. Nonetheless, participants showed lack of knowledge in several areas. 59.2% identified that HPV infections may cause cancer in men. Pandey et al. (2012)⁴ and Patel et al. (2017)⁶ have identified similar gaps in HPV knowledge. This lack of understanding may reduce the argument for gender inclusive vaccination programs. Future healthcare providers need to know that both men and women are at risk of HPV-related anogenital and oropharyngeal cancers. 78.7% of participants recognized HPV types 16 and 18 as major oncogenic strains and demonstrated a fair understanding of the virology involved. However, there were knowledge gaps concerning the vaccine schedule and eligibility criteria, indicating that there are gaps in understanding the practical

aspects of immunization, demonstrating the need for more targeted teaching modules.

TABLE 2: KNOWLEDGE REGARDING HPV INFECTION AND VACCINATION AMONG PARTICIPANTS (N = 272)

Knowledge Variable	Correct Response n (%)
Heard about HPV before joining medical college	207 (76.1)
HPV is a DNA virus	240 (88.2)
Persistent HPV infection can cause cervical cancer	253 (93.0)
HPV types 16 and 18 cause most cervical cancers	214 (78.7)
HPV infection can cause cancers in males	161 (59.2)

Attitude Towards HPV Vaccination

Most of the participants had a positive attitude towards the HPV vaccination. 10 out of 11 participants stated that the HPV vaccination is a recommended way to prevent cervical cancer and should be suggested to patients, by their physicians. This agrees with findings from Mehta et al. (2013)⁵ and Chawla et al. (2016)⁷, who also found supporters of the HPV vaccination as a preventive measure, from the medical students and healthcare professionals that they studied. Greater than 95.2% of participants are in support of giving the HPV vaccination, free of charge, or at a subsidized price. This adds to the understanding of the impact that financial barriers have on the uptake of the HPV vaccination in India, as stated in the publications by Sankaranarayanan et al. (2019)³ and Bruni et al. (2016)⁹. In addition to this, 83.8% of the participants said that they perceive the cost to be a large barrier, which adds to the importance of policy changes regarding this issue. 85.3% of the participants agreed that males should also be vaccinated. This shows changing views on the gender neutral vaccination practice as HPV virus is implicated in oropharyngeal and anogenital cancers. In the context of increasing worldwide recommendations, this is essential.

TABLE 3: ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION (N = 272)

Attitude Statement	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)
HPV vaccination is effective in preventing cervical cancer	246 (90.4)	26 (9.6)
Males should also be vaccinated against HPV	232 (85.3)	40 (14.7)
HPV vaccination should be actively recommended by doctors	251 (92.3)	21 (7.7)
HPV vaccine should be provided free/subsidized	259 (95.2)	13 (4.8)
Cost is a major barrier for HPV vaccination	228 (83.8)	44 (16.2)

Practices Related to HPV Vaccination

Despite satisfactory knowledge and favourable attitudes, actual vaccination uptake was low. Only 13.6% of participants reported having received the HPV vaccine. This discrepancy between knowledge and practice has been consistently observed in previous studies among medical students and healthcare workers, including those by Chawla et al. (2016)⁷ and Holman et al. (2014)¹⁰. Among unvaccinated participants, the most frequently cited barriers were cost (71.1%), lack of adequate information (60.4%), perceived low personal risk (41.7%), and uncertainty regarding eligibility (32.3%). Similar structural and perceptual barriers have been described by

Sankaranarayanan et al. (2019)³ and Holman et al. (2014)¹⁰. These findings suggest that limited access and insufficient practical awareness, rather than negative attitudes, are the primary obstacles to vaccine uptake. Encouragingly, 94.1% of participants expressed willingness to receive vaccination if provided free or at subsidized rates. This indicates that institutional vaccination programs could substantially improve coverage among medical students. Furthermore, 65.4% reported counselling others regarding HPV vaccination, and 89.3% stated that they include HPV advice during patient counselling. While these figures reflect professional responsibility, the low personal vaccination rate highlights a need for self-implementation of preventive practices.

TABLE 4: PRACTICES RELATED TO HPV VACCINATION (N = 272)

Practice Variable	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
Received HPV vaccination	37 (13.6)	235 (86.4)
Willing to get vaccinated if free/subsidized	256 (94.1)	16 (5.9)
Have counselled someone regarding HPV vaccination	178 (65.4)	94 (34.6)
Attended any HPV awareness program	121 (44.5)	151 (55.5)
Include HPV advice during patient counselling	243 (89.3)	29 (10.7)

FIG. 1: HPV VACCINATION STATUS AMONG PARTICIPANTS (N = 272).

his figure depicts the proportion of undergraduate medical students and interns who had received the HPV vaccine. Only 13.6% reported being vaccinated, while 86.4% were not vaccinated, indicating a substantial gap between awareness and vaccination uptake.

Reason	Frequency n (%)
Cost of vaccine	167 (71.1)
Lack of awareness / inadequate information	142 (60.4)
Perceived low personal risk	98 (41.7)
Uncertainty regarding eligibility	76 (32.3)
Concerns regarding side effects	54 (23.0)

TABLE 5: REASONS FOR NON-VACCINATION AGAINST HPV (MULTIPLE RESPONSES ALLOWED, N = 235)

FIG. 2: REASONS FOR NON-VACCINATION AGAINST HPV (N = 235).

This figure illustrates the major barriers to HPV vaccination among unvaccinated participants. Cost (71.1%) was the most frequently cited reason, followed by lack of awareness (60.4%), perceived low personal risk (41.7%), uncertainty regarding eligibility (32.3%), and concerns regarding side effects (23.0%). Multiple responses were permitted.

Implications

The findings underscore a significant knowledge–attitude–practice gap among future healthcare providers. Given the global burden of HPV-related cancers and ongoing cervical cancer elimination initiatives^{1,3}, strengthening medical education through structured academic sessions, awareness campaigns, and on-campus vaccination drives is imperative. Enhancing vaccination uptake among

medical students may have a positive downstream impact on patient counselling, vaccine acceptance, and public health outcomes.

Strengths and Limitations

A key strength of the study is the inclusion of participants from all academic years, including interns, providing a comprehensive overview across different levels of medical training. However, the study has certain limitations. Being a single-centre study, the findings may not be generalizable to all medical colleges. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data may be subject to recall and reporting bias.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights that while undergraduate medical students and interns possess basic

awareness and favourable attitudes towards HPV vaccination, significant gaps in knowledge and poor vaccination practices persist. Addressing these gaps through structured educational interventions and improved access to HPV vaccination is essential to strengthen cervical cancer prevention efforts.

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